
SQUARING THE CIRCLE: A TIMELESS CLASSIC STILL ALIVE AND THRIVING

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ABSTRACT

The classical problem of squaring the circle – namely, the long-pursued task of drawing a square with the same area as a given circle, using only compass and straightedge throughout a finite number of steps – was definitively proven impossible during the 19th century. Approximate constructions remain feasible; for example, rational approximations to any desired level of accuracy can in theory be translated into geometrical constructions. A naive approach, though, would yield impractical procedures requiring finite but overwhelming quantities of steps. Mathematicians therefore have been, and still are, fascinated by the quest for constructions that achieve exceptional precision with respect to the length of the process. In this paper we explore the topic: recalling the underlying approximation of the involved transcendental constants; describing the implemented ranking system, including the adoption of the quantitative approach devised by Lemoine to objectively assess the complexity of geometrical constructions; reviewing some historical milestones and discussing more recent contributions; finally, presenting some original findings, that is, novel approximation formulas – representing noteworthy disclosures in their own right – along with new constructions that substantially expand the boundaries of the conquered territories within this framework.

1 Introduction

Squaring the circle is the most famous of three classical problems from ancient Greek geometry. It is the task of drawing a square with the same area as a given circle, using only compass and straightedge throughout a finite number of steps. In its essence the challenge is equivalent to constructing a segment of length – relative to a reference unit – equal to π or one of its close kin. Over the centuries countless attempts have been undertaken, all doomed to failure: the objective was finally proven impossible in 1882, when Lindemann published [1] the proof that π belongs to the family of *transcendental* numbers, combined with the proof already given in 1837 by Wantzel [2, 3] that such numbers are indeed not constructible. By the way, the same destiny befell the other two ancient problems: doubling the cube and trisecting a generic angle, but “squaring the circle” went on to become the proverbial expression for the pursuit of a solution to an impossible task.

The quest generated not only claims of success later proven faulty, but also some legitimate good approximate constructions, that of course were – and still are – possible. For instance, any fraction can be translated into a compass and straightedge recipe, and notoriously it’s possible to choose a rational number close at will to a given transcendental number. Typically, though, this means choosing fractions with ever-growing denominators: numbers quickly become unwieldy, making conversion into geometrical procedures all but impossible (due to the quantity of required steps and/or to the length of the segments to be drawn). Smarter choices are required.

So, the challenge consists in devising ingenious solutions to combine high precision of the resulting square on one hand, with simplicity – and possibly elegance – on the other [4]. Both characteristics will receive a dedicated section of this work, to explain the quantitative metrics we’ll adopt to enable objective assessments, before moving on to a review of known findings (classical and more recent ones) and finally presenting our new contributions. A final section will feature a table and a chart providing a comprehensive recap of the topic.

2 Approximations and their accuracy

The original problem, as its name suggests, was distinctively geometric in nature. “Squaring” was the standard procedure to “measure” areas, only later replaced with a more numerical approach. For example, while today it’s common to think of a triangle’s area as “base times height divided by two”, Greek mathematicians relied on procedures transforming the triangle into an *equivalent* square (that is, one having the same area), possibly with a rectangle with the same base and half the height as an intermediate step – an embodiment of the modern formula.

In the case of a circle, taking its radius to be (WLOG) equal to 1, we now recognize that the task comes down to drawing a square whose side has a length of $\sqrt{\pi}$, as precisely as possible. Therefore, it’s no surprise that historical advances in this field have gone hand in hand with the search for “good” approximations for π , a task in turn proceeding on its own, aiming at the computation of more and more decimal places while carving concise, efficient, practical formulas. Nowadays the focus has moved toward optimized algorithms, processed by computers to output tremendous quantities of digits, while the original geometrical challenge endures for its own appeal, with less direct connection with mainstream mathematical research efforts.

Given our geometrical purpose, we’ll need to explore formulas which prove suitable for adaptation into constructions with compass and straightedge. It is known (cf. [5] for a modern treatment) that these tools allow the translation into procedures only of finite compositions of the four basic arithmetic operations ($+$, $-$, \times , \div) and square roots¹ – excluding instead, for example, cubic roots and logarithms. The more concise the approximate formula, the easier it is to extract a simple recipe; at the same time, high precision is desirable. To quantitatively evaluate the balance between a construction’s complexity and accuracy, we shall first assess the precision of the underlying approximation. Whether it is provided for π , for $\tau = 2\pi$, directly for $\sqrt{\pi}$ or any other useful value², in agreement with the original problem’s phrasing we’ll rank each formula by the corresponding relative error in the resulting square’s area. Conveniently, this is equivalent to assessing the error in π (which is in fact the value of the area, when $r = 1$), allowing direct comparison among approximations for this famous constant found in varied contexts.

The familiar way of expressing relative errors, that is as percentages, would be impractical, since it would involve numbers with too many zeros (for example, the famous $\pi \approx 355/113$ approximation is correct within 0.0000085%). Of course, adopting scientific notation would be a perfectly valid solution, but we want to promote an even more synthetic and, thus, handier approach; in fact, it is very common in applied sciences when it comes to comparing homogeneous entities, as it effectively addresses the order of magnitude of their ratio: the decibel (dB). Sometimes referred to as a “unit of proportion”, it’s defined as ten times (deci-) the base-10 logarithm (-bel) of the ratio between the investigated quantity (in our case, the error) and a reference value (in our case, the area). So, expressing $|\Delta A|/A$ in dB means calculating $10 \times \log_{10}(|\Delta A|/A)$. Since the error will always be a tiny fraction of the area, we are expecting negative numbers, whose absolute value is roughly related to the number of correct digits of the approximation. The latter is a further alternative metric – quite a common one in fact – but we disapprove of it: while being immediately understandable, and actually functional when it comes to big numbers – in 2024 π was computed to over 2×10^{14} decimal digits – it can be misleading when used for smaller figures. Such method fails to recognize that rounding up, thus losing one “correct” digit, provides a better approximation half of the time, and it neglects that the significance of a digit depends on the magnitude of the most significant (leftmost) one³. Consequently, it may fail at ranking the approximations in correct order – we will in fact encounter one such occurrence.

In the following, we will present various approximation formulas, in particular illustrating – in a sense, literally – those featuring constructible numbers that enabled notable procedures to square the circle.

3 Framework for the evaluation of constructions

The second ingredient for our analysis shall be a metric to assess a construction’s complexity. This is exactly one of the tasks accomplished by the framework devised by Lemoine in the late 19th century [6]. He introduced the concept of “geometrography”, which could be defined with his own words as “the art of geometrical constructions”. Even today,

¹Let’s recall that real numbers are divided into “algebraic” and “transcendental”. That limited set of operations, when applied starting from the unit, is insufficient to express even the entire first subfamily (this would require roots with arbitrary indices, not only multiples of 2), therefore “constructible” numbers form a proper subset of algebraic numbers. Of course, transcendental numbers – as π and its relatives – are even further beyond the scope.

²For example, the square could be constructed from the length of its diagonal, $\sqrt{2} \cdot \sqrt{\pi}$.

³One extreme example: $9.1196 \approx 9.1203$ has an error below 0.008%, but only 1 correct digit after the decimal point, while $1.1196 \approx 1.1104$ has an error above 0.8% – more than one hundred times bigger – despite 2 correct decimal digits. Instead, computing respectively -41 dB and -21 dB shows correctly how the first approximation gives a relative error that is two orders of magnitude smaller.

when handmade compass and straightedge geometry has all but lost its practical usefulness, it is still capable of exerting great fascination by itself. This means that elements of personal taste are unavoidable – we’ll briefly mention them later – but Lemoine’s work has the merit of describing objective criteria to evaluate constructions, first of all their “simplicity”. It is a very convincing approach, at least when it comes to relative comparisons among procedures accomplishing the same task. At its core, the method consists in identifying and then counting the most basic operations into which procedures can be decomposed, such as pointing the compass or drawing a line. We will name them “Lemoine steps”, or “L-steps” for brevity. We will delve into the details shortly, but there is some preceding general information we have to give.

Our constructions will begin with a unit circle, given with its center⁴. Clearly, the procedures are not affected by the absolute length of the radius: if it weren’t set equal to 1, the construction would just scale accordingly. The constructions shall end when the target square has been completely drawn: “squaring the circle” is the traditional objective and there is no justification for shortening the process⁵; neither shall we jeopardize uniformity of comparison allowing different targets such as the (conceptually equivalent, but less common and recognizable) “rectification of the circumference”.

We will indulge in a deviation from the classical, “purest” rules of compass and straightedge constructions: as in DeTemple [7], we will assume the use of a *noncollapsing* compass, that is, one retaining its aperture until intentionally modified – as virtually any real compass does⁶. In other words, it can *transport* lengths. It is proven that anything attainable with a noncollapsing compass can be achieved also with a collapsing one, so allowing the compass to be used according to its normal capabilities is not providing any essential advantage, it just avoids artificial complications making the processes unnecessarily tedious. Instead, we won’t allow further shortcuts: CAD software often provides direct commands to find midpoints, draw parallels, bisect angles... these are given because they are timesavers for operations that could be carried out in a finite number of “regular” steps, so they are not enabling otherwise impossible results. Yet, we are focusing on actual compass and straightedge constructions, and in particular on optimizing them, so allowing such shortcuts would be against the spirit. For the same reason, we will present our drawings including all the pencil marks that would appear on paper when designing by hand, counting the required L-steps accordingly.

Let us now give the details of the framework that we are going to adopt. It is a very slightly customized version of Lemoine’s proposal, relying both on the simplifications given by Mackay in his review of Lemoine’s work [8] and on some further adaptations of ours, always accompanied by their justification. The heart of the approach is the identification of the following construction steps, for which we are introducing a notation that clearly labels them as “setup” operations or “drawing” operations, for both straight lines and circles:

L_s) *To place the edge of the straightedge in coincidence with a point.*

Note: it may be a first point, or a second point while keeping the first one aligned; therefore, the typical preparatory procedure to trace a line through two points⁷ consists in $2 \times L_s$.

L_d) *To draw a straight line.*

C_s) *To point one leg of the compass at one point.*

Note: It may be the pointy leg or the marking leg. Therefore, “taking a measure” will require $2 \times C_s$. If a realignment of the marking leg is needed while keeping the pointy arm fixed, $1 \times C_s$ will suffice.

C_d) *To draw an arc.*

The length of the drawn lines is not accounted for: a short arc will count as $1 \times C_d$ just like a full circle, and a straight line can be long at will. Even if multiple portions of the same line/circle are drawn – typically to avoid overcrowding the drawing’s appearance – they will amount to one step.

We acknowledge some operations that come “for free” and therefore won’t be counted, namely those consisting in quick arbitrary actions with insignificant impact on the construction’s accuracy and complication: marking a random

⁴If the center wasn’t provided, it would be virtually mandatory to start out finding it with a few additional Lemoine steps. We believe this would be just an unnecessary complication, adding no significant insight and only resulting in more crowded drawings.

⁵Someone may argue that upon finding the square’s side, the problem is essentially solved. Actually, it is essentially solved from the moment a constructible approximation is given! But the challenge is providing an efficient construction, and the number of steps remaining after drawing the side is not fixed, depending on the placement of said segment. Moreover, a square could be constructed following different paths, e.g. providing its diagonals.

⁶The “classical” compass should be able to keep a fixed aperture only while drawing a circle, immediately collapsing after the operation. Actually, it’s hard to imagine such an instrument! The fact is, it is just the idealization of the rule “it is possible to draw a circle centered at one point and passing through another point”, given without concern about what kind of tool would materially allow to perform such task.

⁷We won’t allow “recycling” the alignment with a point: each time a pair of points has to be joined a new $2 \times L_s$ operation will be counted. In our experience, trying to “save” one operation would most of the time result in awkward positions, ultimately complicating instead than simplifying the process.

point (even if some restrictions apply, for example it may have to lie on an arc or segment); setting the compass to a random opening (even while keeping the pointy leg fixed); positioning the straightedge or the compass’s pointy leg freely on the plane (again possibly with restrictions, as long as there are, at least locally, two degrees of freedom).

Lemoine distinguished an operation that seems to fall halfway: positioning the pointy leg of the compass on a one-dimensional locus (straight line or arc). Instead, we won’t separate this extremely rare operation from a C_s step⁸. Excessive detail would go beyond the purpose of the framework, that is allowing to rank constructions according to their complexity. For this reason, in any case, steps from different categories – which in turn are already gathering similar but not identical steps – will all be summed with equal weight, resulting in a single summary value⁹. Lemoine calls this comprehensive number of L-steps “coefficient of complication”.

Lemoine proposes also to sum L_s and C_s only, to obtain a “coefficient of inexactitude”. The idea is that those are the steps that, when actually performed by hand, introduce imprecision that keeps accumulating. Again, the approach might enable some direct comparison between constructions, but we disapprove of relying on it to provide any absolute estimation of the actual error affecting a construction, which is known to be a very difficult task [9]. Too many factors play a major role at each step: the angle at which two lines intersect, how close two points defining a segment are, how far a segment is extended... Sometimes some clever *additional* steps addressing these factors can *lower* the error! Therefore, while coming back on this topic again, we won’t really trust L_s and C_s for quantitative purposes.

On the other hand, we also disapprove of the oversimplified approach, quite common in fact, that involves summing only L_d and C_d to give the number of “steps”. It fails to promote a real optimization of constructions in terms of simplicity; for example, it fails to recognize that drawing a random line (e.g. a chord of a circle whose center has to be found: $0 \times L_s + 1 \times L_d$) is quicker and less demanding than drawing one that has to join two points ($2 \times L_s + 1 \times L_d$). Moreover, even though we don’t approve the use of L_s and C_s for quantitative assessment, they are undeniably responsible for the imprecision affecting actual handmade drawings, so their significance should not be underestimated.

A few last words about the aforementioned elements of subjectivity that cannot be denied when the “elegance” of a construction is acknowledged, the most obvious being the aesthetic appeal of the overall drawing. While it’s all but impossible to quantify the beauty of a construction, we can give a non-exhaustive list of qualitative, vaguely defined factors that we believe contribute to the finesse of a design:

- a meaningful point should not be too close to a line it doesn’t belong to;
- two meaningful points should not be too close to each other;
- intersections defining a point should not happen at too acute angles;
- the smallest detail and the largest distance should be compatible.

The last one in particular translates to a practical requirement: the minimum and maximum compass openings should not be disproportionate with respect to the scale of the overall drawing, and in particular their ratio should be kept relatively small, so that one – preferably single – compass can actually carry out the task throughout the entire procedure. For some of the constructions we are going to present, we will give this “compass ratio” as secondary information. In fact, we have constantly kept an eye on *all* these elegance characteristics, but always giving higher priority to the construction’s “simplicity”, that is settling for less elegant solutions whenever they allowed us to save one or more steps.

4 State of the art

Now, equipped with the evaluation tools previously described, our first commitment will be to revisit the significant milestones that have marked the human pursuit of squaring the circle. Considering the ingenuity they reveal, it’s especially fitting to say that we will be outlining the “state of the art”. In particular, we will call “cornerstones” those findings that stand unmatched in terms of precision versus complexity: as a chart will clearly illustrate, a construction sits in a corner when no other is able to provide an equal or smaller error requiring an equal or smaller number of L-steps. In other words, all other constructions are either less precise, more complicated, or both.

To enable a fair comparison, we have made every effort to ensure that each construction is optimized according to our framework: their authors had indeed simplicity in mind, but they were not aware or not interested in refined quantitative metrics like the one we have established. So, we have always tried to minimize the number of L-steps, in particular

⁸Pointing on a line should offer one additional degree of freedom with respect to a point, but Mackay notes that a similar line of thought should then be applied to L_s too: both translation and rotation can be used to align the straightedge with the first point, but only rotation for the second.

⁹Assigning different weights to the various actions would be overkill, especially considering that most of the time the counters grow roughly in proportion, making it common to see “competing” constructions with all of them consistently higher or lower.

when the procedures required completion, but also when some minor adjustments, respectful of the original proposals, allowed higher efficiency. We have no proof that our results are optimal, but we did our best to ensure a uniform standard.

Let’s start our journey: we’ll go through the classical findings in order of increasing precision. To set things in motion, we cannot but start mentioning one of the most ancient and famous approximations for π , namely $\pi \approx 3 + 1/7 = 22/7$. Actually, there is no correspondingly widely accepted classical construction based on this simple fraction, so we undertook the task. The most direct approach required 50 L-steps, which we could lower to 46 with a trick whose main drawback is raising the compass ratio to the unrealistic value of 196. Anyway, we are not going to picture the outcome here: we are reserving room for the most significant findings, and this one will be overshadowed in a short time.

The first really classical construction we encounter is that from Kochanski. The approximation formula itself, $\pi \approx \sqrt{40/3 - 2\sqrt{3}}$ is still known by the name of this Polish mathematician, who proposed the construction derived thereof in 1685 [10, 11]. For the time, it represented an exceptional finding, that remains notable to this day thanks to its simplicity combined with the fair accuracy it conveys (-47.2 dB). In fact, it turns out to be at the same time slightly simpler but also twenty times more precise than our mentioned attempt with $22/7$, justifying its dismissal. For the present analysis, in addition to optimizing the original construction by Kochanski, we have also found a slightly different way to exploit the same approximation which happens to require exactly the same number of L-steps, precisely 45. Here we are presenting this version, both to offer an alternative to the standard one, easily found online¹⁰, and because it results in a nicer overall outcome (with a compass ratio as low as 3):

Figure 1: Kochanski (1685)

We now leap to the beginning of the 20th century, presenting the proposal given by Hobson in 1913 [12]. This is the oldest documented construction we are aware of that takes advantage of the approximation involving the golden ratio¹¹, $\pi \approx 6/5 \varphi^2$, which will prove to be the most prolific seed in our treatment. With a -48.1 dB relative error, it happens to be slightly more precise than Kochanski’s formula, despite the count of “correct decimal digits” seems to say the opposite. Hobson’s construction is also a fitting example of the kind of optimization we felt authorized to introduce in the procedures: as often happens, the author didn’t supply all the minor details of the recipe – such as how to find a given fraction of a segment – so that we are called to “fill in the gaps”, and we find it fair to do that in the most efficient way¹². Our final result is a construction requiring 59 L-steps:

¹⁰See for example Wikipedia’s entry on this topic, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Squaring_the_circle#Approximate_constructions, where this and some other classical constructions are presented.

¹¹Recall that the *golden ratio* is the famous constant $\varphi = \frac{\sqrt{5}+1}{2}$ satisfying the equation $\varphi^2 = \varphi + 1$.

¹²In this case Hobson requires drawing a semicircle whose diameter is the segment $[-3/5, 1/2]$, without specifying how to find these extremes, whose midpoint $-1/20$ would be the center at which to point the compass. We found that locating the same center as the midpoint of $[-1/2, 2/5]$ happens to be much faster, and then proceed by drawing the semicircle originally required. Nor did Hobson say how or when to draw the perpendicular lines through the given circle’s center: instinctively drawn as the first thing, we found instead that postponing one axis a few steps allowed us to take advantage of already drawn geometries.

Figure 2: Hobson (1913)

Still in the early 1900s, Ramanujan published [13] many approximation formulas for π . Among them we find the one we just saw Hobson use, expressed in the alternative elegant form $\pi \approx 9/5 + \sqrt{9/5}$, and the slightly more precise (at -50.0 dB) $\pi \approx \frac{7}{3} + \frac{7}{5\sqrt{3}}$. He didn't provide geometric constructions derived from either of them. As anticipated, we will repeatedly encounter the first one later on; at this point, we report that our efforts with the second one led to a best outcome requiring 69 L-steps, a result which will not measure up to the following.

We now take a step back to the 19th century. In 1828, Specht published [14] a construction that today appears largely forgotten, although it features commendable metrics. Maybe the formula it's based on, $\tau = 2\pi \approx \frac{13}{25}\sqrt{146}$, is not very appealing; but, despite the challenging numbers involved, Specht was able to embed it in a particularly simple construction with respect to the -66.5 dB precision it yields. As usual, he didn't provide all the details, so we have refined our best completion to provide a full squaring procedure, amounting to 67 L-steps:

In 1849, Jacob de Gelder published [15] a brilliant compass and straightedge rendering of the famous rational approximation $\pi \approx 355/113$. First discovered by the Chinese mathematician Zu Chongzhi in the 5th century, and surprisingly accurate (-70.7 dB) for such a small denominator, this fraction would anyway require quite an involved process if it weren't for de Gelder smartly re-expressing it as $\pi \approx 3 + 4^2/(7^2+8^2)$. We have devised our best continuation to his construction¹³, completing the squaring in 73 L-steps (not benefiting from focused optimization efforts, the compass ratio escalates to 14.63):

$\pi \approx 355/113$
 $|\Delta A|/A = -70.7$ dB
 Lemoine steps: 73

	Ls	Ld	Cs	Cd	
circle at O	0	0	0	0	
NS, SZ = NZ	1	1	2	2	ON = OS = 1
NH = HO	2	1	1	1	OH = 1/2
NQ = QH	2	1	1	1	OQ = 3/4
NT = TQ	2	1	1	1	OT = 7/8
WE \perp NS	2	1	0	0	OE = OW = 1
ET	2	1	0	0	ET = 1/8 $\sqrt{(7^2 + 8^2)} = 1/8 \sqrt{113}$
OH = EG	0	0	3	1	
GT = GA = GB	0	0	2	1	
GT = AC = BC	0	0	2	2	
GC \perp OE \rightarrow I	2	1	0	0	EI = 4 / $\sqrt{113}$
GJ // TI	2	1	3	2	EJ = EI^2 = 16/113
EJ = EK	0	0	2	1	
EL = LK	2	1	1	1	
LW = LV	0	0	2	1	OV = $\sqrt{(355/113)} \approx \sqrt{\pi}$
square on OV	4	2	4	3	area $\approx \pi$
	21	11	24	17	
	tot 73				

Figure 4: de Gelder (1849)

Along with the construction mentioned earlier, Specht published another one which is equally forgotten, if not more so. Again based on a not-so-friendly formula, $\tau \approx 5\sqrt{439/278}$, the construction requires some additional L-steps, totaling 81, but it provides a remarkably low error at -83.7 dB. We may only say that, according to our criteria, elegance isn't the best trait of this drawing, shown in Fig. 5.

The pinnacle of classical findings is that from Ramanujan. In 1914, the Indian genius disclosed [13] both the approximation and the construction. His wonderful formula provided an unbelievable precision (-94.9 dB) for such a concise expression: $\pi \approx \sqrt[4]{2143/22}$. Ramanujan himself must have been very proud of this finding, if it's true what he's reported to have claimed: that the Goddess of Namagiri appeared to him to reveal the true value of π . This constructible number¹⁴ was actually expressed as $\sqrt[4]{9^2 + 19^2/22}$, a form that thanks to clever sleights allowed Ramanujan to offer a procedure which leads to the squaring – again after our most efficient completion – in 106 Lemoine steps, as shown in Fig. 6 (as usual not prioritized, the compass ratio further grows to 16.04). He also gave a numerical example to help visualize the amazing accuracy achieved: when squaring a circle as large as the Earth's equator, the square's side would be off by less than 2 mm. In terms of precision of the approximation – and possibly of the ingenuity of the derived construction¹⁵ – Ramanujan's feat has stood as the benchmark for more than a century.

It's a good moment to stop and take a look at the situation. We believe that the constructions described so far can be considered the “classical” ones: they were given in times when drawings were still actually done by hand, when computer aid was not available, neither for design nor for computations related to the approximations. Let us collect such findings in a two-dimensional chart (Fig. 7) where the horizontal placement represents a drawing's complexity and the vertical one the relative error of the resulting square's area. We are highlighting the portion of the chart that has been “conquered”, that is, zones where the combination of precision-vs-complexity is not better than that achieved by some cornerstone. The challenge for new constructions is to expand this territory, improving at least one of the metrics featured by previous findings.

¹³Some decades later, Ramanujan gave his proposal based on this approximation, but de Gelder's one remains quantitatively simpler.

¹⁴A 4th root is obtained chaining two square roots.

¹⁵Which embeds such precision into a process still proving “practical” to execute (there is no objective threshold here). As said, in theory any accuracy is attainable, if unwieldy procedures are admitted.

Figure 5: Specht No. 2 (1828)

$\pi \approx (2143/22)^{1/4}$
 $|\Delta A|/A = -94.9 \text{ dB}$
 Lemoine steps: 106

	Ls	Ld	Cs	Cd	
circle at O	0	0	0	0	
WE, EZ = WZ	1	1	2	2	OW = OE = 1
WO = WA	0	0	1	1	
NS ⊥ WE	2	1	0	0	ON = OS = 1
AE → B	2	1	0	0	
OB = OC = OD	0	0	2	1	
DC → T	2	1	0	0	OT = 1/3
OT = SJ = JK	0	0	2	2	SJ = JK = 1/3
OT = EG	0	0	2	1	GE = 1/3
EB = EF → EF ⊥ OE	2	1	1	1	
EK, EJ	4	2	0	0	EK = $\sqrt{(2 + 4/9)}$, EJ = $\sqrt{(2 + 1/9)}$
EJ = EL	0	0	2	1	
LM // KJ	2	1	4	3	EM = $EJ^2 / EK = 1/3 \cdot \sqrt{(19^2 / 22)}$
GH // OM	2	1	5	2	EH = 1/3 EM = $1/9 \cdot \sqrt{(2143/22 - 9^2)}$
EH = EI	0	0	2	1	$\approx \sqrt{(\pi^4 / 9^2 - 1)}$
OI = OP	0	0	2	1	OP = OI $\approx \pi^2 / 9$
OX = XP	2	1	2	2	
XP = XQ	0	0	2	1	
OQ = OR	0	0	2	1	OR = OQ $\approx \pi / 3$
OY = YR	2	1	2	2	
RY = RU	0	0	2	1	OU $\approx \pi / 2$
UO = UV	0	0	2	1	OV $\approx \sqrt{\pi}$
side OV → square	4	2	4	3	area $\approx \pi$
	25	13	41	27	
	tot 106				

Figure 6: Ramanujan (1914)

Figure 7: Classical compass and straightedge constructions for squaring the circle

We are now going to review some more recent contributions, going through them in chronological order. We'll find them as we jump to the turn of the 21st century; we shall begin though by mentioning an approximation whose origin is actually hard to trace: Popper conjectured that Plato was aware of it, but admittedly without any direct evidence [16]; the formula as we know it is likely much more recent. It reads: $\pi \approx \sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$. It's interesting because of its simple and elegant form, whereas its accuracy, at -28.3 dB, is pretty low¹⁶, to a level that we arbitrarily consider to be the minimum to deserve inclusion in the present collection. We are not even aware of any classical construction based on this formula; however, it's such a concise expression that extracting a correspondingly simple recipe from it requires no exceptional skill. We undertook the task and we got to a procedure entailing 41 Lemoine steps: a notable result, being the smallest count we've encountered so far.

In 1991 we find again the -48.1 dB approximation based on the golden ratio, when Dixon [17] gives an alternative construction to Hobson's; but, comparing them after our usual optimization, we find that 60 L-steps do not improve upon the already reported 59: we'll have to wait some further years for a substantial update to this contest.

Meanwhile, in 2002, Schneider [18] finds a very nice formula: $\pi \approx \sqrt{7 + \sqrt{6 + \sqrt{5}}}$. We put it to the test as the base for a construction and we obtained an outcome of 72 L-steps, actually not impressive with respect to its -49.0 dB accuracy. Schneider himself says that the expression's merit is primarily aesthetic rather than practical, but we believe he might be underrating its utility as a mnemonic tool¹⁷. We find it superior, for example, to the well-known $\pi \approx \sqrt[3]{31}$, which is less precise (-41.7 dB) and not even constructible. Shortly after, in 2006 Joseph [19] discloses the charming $\pi \approx (\ln 6)^{(\ln 5)^{(\ln 4)^{(\ln 3)^{(\ln 2)}}}}$; this number is actually more precise (-53.1 dB), but not really handy and again not constructible.

¹⁶Its error is three times larger than that of the famous truncated value 3.14, which in turn is a slightly coarser approximation than $22/7$.

¹⁷Moreover, it can be conveniently computed on a simple handheld calculator with an uninterrupted sequence of key strokes:

$$\boxed{5} \quad \boxed{\sqrt{}} \quad \boxed{+} \quad \boxed{6} \quad \boxed{=} \quad \boxed{\sqrt{}} \quad \boxed{+} \quad \boxed{7} \quad \boxed{=} \quad \boxed{\sqrt{}}$$

In 2019 it's the time of a paper from Chu [20], which acts on two fronts. First, he offers a further try with the golden ratio approximation. He explicitly claims an improvement over Dixon's proposal; according to our best adaptations he is still up by one L-step (61 vs 60), but more importantly he doesn't take into account the older achievement (59) by Hobson. Then he drafts a procedure to turn a never-before-used formula into a construction. It's an interesting initiative: $\pi \approx \frac{63}{25} \times \frac{17+15\sqrt{5}}{7+15\sqrt{5}}$ offers the unprecedented precision of -101.6 dB, a significant leap beyond Ramanujan's iconic formula! What we cannot agree with is his claim that the constructions are roughly equally as complicated. Chu's instructions are not complete, but even providing our best implementation of his sketched outlines, we couldn't finalize the process in less than 150 L-steps, likely even more. Such complication will make this attempt short-lived in our analysis.

The last entry of this section – yet another attempt with the golden ratio formula – is particularly interesting, not only because it finally succeeds in providing a substantially simpler recipe, but also because of the accompanying line of thought. In his 2022 paper, Beatrix [21] points out that the error introduced when actually executing the drawings by hand largely exceeds the intrinsic one of the approximations, so that, in reality, the most precise outcome is obtained with the procedure which – provided that the approximation itself is not too coarse – requires the minimum number of steps. While we totally agree with the principle, we reaffirm that quantifying the magnitude of the induced error is a task that would require finer tools than those we are adopting: truly assessing the error propagation throughout a geometrical construction is indeed a formidable challenge [9]. Beatrix instead relies on Lemoine's work for a *quantitative* estimation of the error's growth with the number of steps. Ironically, he proceeds by adopting the oversimplified metric that takes into account only the "drawing" steps and disregards the "setup" steps, thus failing to promote the targeted minimization of those very operations that impact the construction's inaccuracy! Anyway, he really does offer a procedure which finally improves – and quite substantially, requiring 46 L-steps – upon the ones by Chu, Dixon and Hobson, the latter enduring as the simplest for over a century. Let us spotlight Beatrix's efficient strategy, that is, targeting directly the square's side with $\sqrt{\pi} \approx \sqrt{6/5} \varphi$. He also subjectively claims that his drawing, depicted below, looks particularly elegant and, not only because of the low compass ratio ($= 3.54$), we undoubtedly agree:

Figure 8: Beatrix (2022)

The fact is, Beatrix probably wasn't aware that Kochanski's construction could be optimized as much as we have shown, so that their achievements end up in a substantial tie: in our framework, the constructions are sitting almost in the same spot, being separated by just a single L-step and a single dB of precision.

5 New findings

In this section we will present our original results, specifying the varying reasons why we believe they provide interesting contributions to the topic.

Let's resume from where we left off, that is, with Beatrix's work, since our first construction is again based on the golden ratio approximation, again aiming directly at the square's side with $\sqrt{\pi} \approx \sqrt{6/5} \varphi$. We are providing a further significant reduction of the steps required to translate this expression into a construction. Let's recall that we agree with Beatrix – despite not approving his quantitative statements – that the lowest number of operations guarantees the smallest imprecision when actually performing a drawing by hand, provided that the theoretical accuracy is good enough not to be the limiting factor, as it's certainly true at -48.1 dB. To put this number in perspective, squaring a circle like those depicted in these pictures – with a diameter of, say, 5 cm – the intrinsic inaccuracy would be well below half a micrometer ($1/1000$ of a mm). It's pretty obvious that in a real drawing this contribution to the square's side error would be negligible! Since we succeeded lowering the complication down to 38 L-steps¹⁸, fewer than any previous result, we shall venture to claim that our finding represents the most precise compass and straightedge procedure available to date to manually square the circle. The construction (minimal and clean indeed, and with a compass ratio as low as 3) is shown here:

Figure 9: Squaring the circle – Novel construction No. 1

To introduce our next finding, let us recall that we encountered formulas which are visually appealing, and thus easy to remember, even though they didn't enable notable compass and straightedge constructions. Let us take the opportunity to mention a few other unacknowledged¹⁹ expressions in the same spirit: $\pi \approx \sqrt{9.87}$, providing -47.0 dB of precision (despite its compactness and computational handiness, we couldn't convert it into a reasonably simple drawing), and the nice $\pi \approx 10^{2/3} - 3/2$ and $\tau \approx \log_2(77.88)$, rated respectively at -59.2 dB and -61.6 dB but not constructible.

Here we are at the nicest of our expressions: $\tau \approx 6^{1/2} + 6^{3/4}$. Of course, we have no objective metrics to support what we are venturing to claim: we believe that this is the best mnemonic formula available, correlating how easy it is to remember²⁰ with the accuracy it offers (-52.3 dB). It's also a constructible number, and the simplest procedure we extracted from it, requiring 65 L-steps, is technically a cornerstone, though not a game-changer (our previous

¹⁸If we wanted to compare with Beatrix's proposal adopting his metrics – differing from ours in many respects – we'd still confirm the improvement at 11 vs 13 steps.

¹⁹We couldn't find these expressions mentioned elsewhere, but they appear quite simple and we don't dare claim authorship.

²⁰And the fact that it can be easily computed on a simple calculator, namely with the sequence:

$$6 \times 6 \times 6 = \sqrt{\sqrt{6} + 6} \sqrt{6}$$

construction is much simpler being only slightly less precise, while the first one from Specht was much more accurate requiring just a couple more L-steps). Here it is:

Figure 10: Squaring the circle – Novel construction No. 2

If, visually speaking, the formula above was the nicest, we believe the one we are about to present is our overall most remarkable. Here it is: $\pi \approx 9/8 + (1/7 + \sqrt{11/10})^4$. Of course, we can't rule out some subjectivity when appraising how elegant an expression is, but we may highlight its neat structure: it includes only basic operations applied to simple fractions, which in turn showcase a bunch of small consecutive integers, from 7 to 11, in an orderly arrangement. Meanwhile, it provides the exceptional precision²¹ of -107.4 dB ! This translates to an error 20 times smaller than that provided by Ramanujan's iconic formula which, we believe, has a comparable level of complexity (trading the number of elements for their size). We underline again how impressive that finding was, considering that no electronic aids were available at the time; it was precise enough to be semi-seriously declared "the true value of π " and, to our knowledge, until now no other simple formula had been made available with similar or higher precision. The simplicity of our new expression allowed us also to devise a construction that is a few L-steps simpler than Ramanujan's, namely 99 vs 106, temporarily claiming its position as the most precise cornerstone in our diagram. The honestly not-so-elegant construction (with a very high compass ratio: 21.49) is depicted²² in fig. 11.

Our last contribution features a new formula to target the square's side: $\sqrt{\pi} \approx 2 - \sqrt{2/3 + \sqrt{2}/8} / (9/5 + \sqrt{5})$. It appears more convoluted than the previous one, but it actually admitted a surprisingly efficient transposition into a compass and straightedge construction, letting us square the circle with an outstanding -117.3 dB precision in as few as 89 L-steps. Let us compare again these figures with the classical benchmark, Ramanujan's finding: with a procedure requiring 16% fewer steps, the error is now being reduced 200 times. To convey the level of precision, the theoretical inaccuracy affecting the square's side, when squaring circles like those in these pages, would be on the order of $1/1000$ of an atom's size! Sticking to Ramanujan's example, squaring the Earth's equator – a circle with a diameter of 12 756 km – would result in an error of approximately 0.01 mm. The drawing is shown in Fig. 12; allow us to accompany it with a personal judgment: not only does this construction show remarkable metrics, but we find it also particularly elegant according to all the factors we have listed before (no points are too close, no intersections happen at very acute angles, the compass ratio is as low as 6.38...).

²¹On the typical 10-digit display of handheld scientific calculators this approximate value is finally indistinguishable from the actual π .

²²In this execution point P falls very close to J, $\sqrt{10}$ being a decent approximation of π by itself. This proximity can easily be avoided by placing P on the over side (i.e. to the left of O, in our drawing): the number of steps is unchanged, the tradeoff is that the design further expands significantly in width.

Figure 11: Squaring the circle – Novel construction No. 3

Figure 12: Squaring the circle – Novel construction No. 4

6 Conclusions

In this work we have reviewed the history of the proverbial challenge known as “squaring the circle”, according to its original mathematical meaning: looking for a compass and straightedge construction that allows the drawing of a square whose area is the same as that of a given circle – actually, given the proven impossibility of an exact outcome, as close as possible to it. We have described how we chose to express the precision of the approximation formulas and to assess the simplicity of the constructions derived thereof, which aim to provide the best accuracy-to-complication ratio. We have then gone through classical findings, we have reviewed more recent contributions and we have finally introduced some results of ours.

Here we recap all such milestones, first of all presenting the up-to-date chart (Fig. 13) where constructions are placed according to the relative error of the resulting square’s area, expressed in decibel, against the complexity of the procedure, measured in terms of the required Lemoine steps. For both attributes, the lower the better: constructions that provide the best precision for their level of complication sit in bottom-left corners of the chart’s region that has been “conquered”. A new finding expands this territory if it lands outside the shadows already cast by previous ones; as for the novel constructions presented in this work, we are highlighting their contribution by using a different shade.

Figure 13: Up-to-date collection of constructions for squaring the circle

Finally, we also provide Table 1 gathering the most interesting approximation formulas, listing all those that enabled significant procedures to square the circle, for which we give the complication level and the author/year of disclosure. We are also including some particularly interesting or elegant expressions (with no objective criterion) mentioned throughout this work even if, featuring non-constructible numbers, they don’t translate to compass and straightedge drawings. The list is given in order of increasing precision, with the relative error reported referring always to the square’s area; as a result, it conveniently also applies to the accuracy of the approximation of π itself (or $\tau = 2\pi$) even if the constructions typically rely on building the square’s side, which should be as close as possible to $\sqrt{\pi}$ (in fact, formulas that directly approximate this value enabled very efficient procedures).

Before taking our leave we want to emphasize how the challenge of squaring the circle is among the oldest mathematical topics enduring into the 21st century, having crossed more than two millennia. Over time it changed shape, surviving both the decline of the original practical motivations and the proof that no exact solution can exist. Quite paradoxically, the latter is exactly what provided certainty that the quest will never come to a definite end: enhancements will always be possible, making this age-old pursuit immortal.

*As the geometer his mind applies
To square the circle, nor for all his wit
Finds the right formula, howe’er he tries*
Dante Alighieri
(Divine Comedy, ca. 1321)

Table 1: Notable approximations and compass and straightedge constructions for squaring the circle

Approximation	$\frac{ \Delta A }{A}$	L-steps	Publication
$\pi \approx \sqrt{2} + \sqrt{3}$	-28.3 dB	41	
$\pi \approx 3 + \frac{1}{7} = \frac{22}{7}$	-34.0 dB	46	
$\pi \approx \sqrt[3]{31}$	-41.7 dB	-	
$\pi \approx \sqrt{9.87}$	-47.0 dB	> 150	
$\pi \approx \sqrt{\frac{40}{3} - 2\sqrt{3}}$	-47.2 dB	45	Kochanski (1685)
$\sqrt{\pi} \approx \sqrt{\frac{6}{5}} \varphi$	-48.1 dB	38	present work
$\pi \approx \sqrt{7 + \sqrt{6 + \sqrt{5}}}$	-49.0 dB	72	Schneider ²³ (2008)
$\pi \approx \frac{7}{3} + \frac{7}{5\sqrt{3}}$	-50.0 dB	69	Ramanujan ²³ (1914)
$\tau \approx 6^{1/2} + 6^{3/4}$	-52.3 dB	65	present work
$\pi \approx (\ln 6)^{(\ln 5)^{(\ln 4)^{(\ln 3)^{(\ln 2)}})}$	-53.1 dB	-	Joseph ²³ (2006)
$\pi \approx 10^{\frac{2}{3}} - \frac{3}{2}$	-59.2 dB	-	
$\tau \approx \log_2(77.88)$	-61.6 dB	-	
$\tau \approx \frac{13}{25}\sqrt{146}$	-66.5 dB	67	Specht (1828)
$\pi \approx \frac{355}{113}$	-70.7 dB	73	de Gelder (1849)
$\tau \approx 5\sqrt{\frac{439}{278}}$	-83.7 dB	81	Specht (1828)
$\pi \approx \sqrt[4]{\frac{2143}{22}}$	-94.9 dB	106	Ramanujan (1914)
$\pi \approx \frac{9}{8} + \left(\frac{1}{7} + \sqrt{\frac{11}{10}}\right)^4$	-107.4 dB	99	present work
$\sqrt{\pi} \approx 2 - \frac{\sqrt{2/3 + \sqrt{2}/8}}{9/5 + \sqrt{5}}$	-117.3 dB	89	present work

²³These authors provided only the formula; for constructible numbers, we devised the simplest construction we could.

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